

Yoga Attitude as a Determinate of Peace Awareness in Relation to Their Gender And Stream

Neeru Yadav

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Education, R.B.S. College, Agra

Mob.: 7017698006

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Abstract

This study was undertaken to assess yoga attitude as a determinate of peace awareness in relation to their gender and stream at senior secondary level. A sample of 60 students (30 male (15 Science and 15 Commerce Stream) and 30 female students (15 Science and 15 Commerce Stream) were drawn by using random sampling technique from Agra district. Whereas yoga attitude and peace awareness of students was considered as the independent variable, the variable like gender (male and female only) and different Stream (Science and Commerce only) were considered as the categorical variable. Yoga attitude was assessed by *Yoga Attitude Scale (YAS)* prepared by **Dr. Mahesh Kumar Muchhal**. Peace awareness was assessed *PEACE AWARENESS SCALE (PAS-AA)* prepared by **Dr. Anjum Ahmad**. By After analysing data, the findings revealed that there are no significant differences in the yoga attitude and peace awareness of secondary level students. A quantitative descriptive survey done on 60 randomised sample which analysed through MS Excel.

Keywords: Yoga Attitude & Peace Awareness.

Introduction

"If we are to teach real peace in this world and if we are to carry on a real war, we shall have to begin with the children."

- M. K. Gandhi

The highest objective of all education is inculcating and imbibing peace and harmony in human life. The mother is the first teacher of their children and teaches them the peace and values of family, society and nations. Peace and values nurtured at home again enhanced at school. Peace, a state of inner calm and end of the conflict, is a broad concept with spiritual values and social connotation. Peace is the wellbeing of the human mind and society such as harmony, accord, security and understanding.

Background

India has projected the universal idea of cosmic unity and the universal brotherhood of the welfare of humankind. India has a holy and peaceful vision of the whole world as a happy family like "*Sarvebhavantusukhina*" means may all be happy or may all beings be happy. It is a universal prayer promoting peace, compassion and well-being for everyone, often extended to include freedom from illness and suffering. India always visualized the earth as a global village like "*Vasudhaivakutumbakam*" means the whole world feels like a family. It is a basic mantra of peace and universal unity global peace may be defined as a state of wellbeing of the universe which can we experienced though a very good co-existence and mutual understanding between a different country of the world.

Thus, it can say that India has a long and vibrant history in promoting peace, international understanding, tolerance and self-restraint which are given in detail infamous and holy books like *Vedas, Puranas, and Upanishads*. India is a multi-cultural, multi-ethnic, multi-lingual, and multi-religious country has to learn to live with it to its best advantage harmonious living together in India. India has a great view of peace and gave '*Shanti Patha*' to the whole world.

Om Dayoah Shanti Rantariksham Shanti
Prithvi Shantirapah Shantiah
Aushadhaya: Shanti: Vanaspati: Shanti:
Vishvedeva: Shanti: Brahma Shanti:
Sarvam shantih shantireva shantih
Sama Shantiredhah
Om shantih, shantih, shantih!

Need

Frustration, anxiety, mental stress and mental related diseases etc. are increasing day by day in our society. Due to these diseases many persons including the students feels isolation, anger, confusion, depression, mood disorders, attention deficit-hyperactive disorder, obsessive disorder, adjustment disorder etc. Yoga attitude would give the proper direction for the betterment in positive peace awareness. The present study tries to provide a clear-cut concept of the students' yoga attitude and their peace awareness.

It is said that if anyone who is to spread real peace in the world, it shall begin with the children. The children of today will be the next citizen of tomorrow. The young generation is strong pillars of any society, nation, and world. These children may be the messengers of peace and harmony in the world facing war, injustice, and prejudice against colour, gender, and race etc. Only educational institutions can help to achieve that goal where the young minds are trained to understand the deeper meaning of peace and spiritual values. It also helps to train to be a positive self-concept with a yoga attitude.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are as under:

- O1.** To study the yoga attitude as a determinant of peace awareness of secondary level students.
- O2.** To study the yoga attitude as a determinant of peace awareness in relation to gender of secondary level students.
 - i)** To study the yoga attitude in relation to gender of secondary level students.
 - ii)** To study the peace awareness in relation to gender of secondary level students.
- O3.** To study the yoga attitude as a determinant of peace awareness in relation to stream of secondary level students.
 - i)** To study the yoga attitude in relation to stream of secondary level students.
 - ii)** To study the peace awareness in relation to stream of secondary level students.

Hypotheses

The following Major hypotheses were formulated for the present study:

- H₀ 1:** There are no significant difference between yoga attitude and peace awareness of secondary level students.
- H₀ 2 (i):** There are no significant difference between male and female students of yoga attitude.
- H₀ 2 (ii):** There are no significant difference between male and female students of peace awareness.
- H₀ 3 (i):** There are no significant difference between science and commerce students of yoga attitude.
- H₀ 3 (ii):** There are no significant difference between science and commerce students of peace awareness.

Delimitations

1. The present study delimited to Agra district of UP.
2. The present study delimited to secondary level students.
3. The present study delimited to CBSE students.
4. The study was delimited to 5 schools only.

Operational definition of the terms used

Yoga Attitude

Yoga means 'union' or 'connection'. Conscious connection to something allows us to feel and experience that thing, person or experience. The experience of connection is a state of yoga, a joyful, blissful and fulfilling experience. Awareness is the secret of yoga. It claims to improve health and

happiness. Attitude is defined as ‘a complex mental state involving beliefs and feeling’. Attitudes are generally positive or negative views of a person, place, thing or event. Yoga attitude means the feeling, beliefs and views of students towards yoga.

Peace Awareness

The principles of peace are described variously in Hindu Dharma in which taught the highly spiritualistic philosophy of non-difference of self and others. It believes in the existence of *Ishwar* is everywhere and in all-pervasive self-effulgent energy and consciousness. It creates a strong belief and attitude toward sublime tolerance and acceptance toward others. All human beings are the same and are created from the same God so there should be a sense of equality and one should not harm or hurt others. According to Indian philosophy, the concept of peace is established on the principles of *Non-Difference of Self and Others*. Peace in Indian culture, the highest human values are interlinked with other values such as with truth, friendliness, tolerance and peaceful attitude is regarded as the foundation of all morality.

As an eye bird on Indian history, it could find mentioning of such as ethical, spiritual and peaceful virtues in the *Vedas, Upanishads, Puranas, Ramayana, Mahabharata, Bhagwat Gita* and different schools of Indian philosophy. To understand the Indian views of peace and harmony it becomes essential to discuss the views and philosophy of *Mahatma Gandhi, Ravindranath Tagore, Sri Chaitanya Maha Prabhu, Swami Ramakrishna, and Swami Vivekananda, etc.* Many notable persons in India worked for peace. Out of them, some famous persons like *Gautam Buddha, Bhagwan Mahavir, Kabir, Shankaracharya, Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Aurobindo, Baba Amte, Mother Teresa, Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, Medha Patekar, and Kailash Satyarthi, etc* all of these worked for peace all life.

Design

In order to get proper reflection as per objectives, the descriptive survey research method aroused. Descriptive and inferential statistics are employed to analyse data for reaching a valid and generalized conclusion.

Sample

The sample selected randomly from different secondary level students. The students from co-ed schools of Agra district. 60 students taken as sample by randomised way for this study.

Sample Structure			
Stream	Male	Female	Total
Science	15	15	30
Commerce	15	15	30
Total	30	30	60

Major variables

- i. Yoga Attitude
- ii. Peace awareness

Categorical variables

- i. Sex (boys & girls)
- ii. Stream (Science & Commerce)

Tools

- i. Yoga attitude - *Yoga Attitude Scale (YAS)* by Dr. Mahesh Kumar Muchhal.
- ii. Peace awareness - *PEACE AWARENESS SCALE (PAS-AA)* by Dr. Anjum Ahmad.

Procedure of Data Collection

The researcher visited to the school personally and to the school students given short instruction regarding the filing in of their response. After that, the tool proceed to them and the required approximately 30 minutes for completing. Collected data is tabulated and organized for presentation, analysis and interpretation. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses used for data analysis. Descriptive and inferential statistics are applied. The significance of t- values tested at 0.05 level of significance. Whole data analysed through MS Excel.

Hypotheses Testing

Testing of H₀1:

H₀ 1: There are no significant difference between yoga attitude and peace awareness of secondary level students.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Yoga attitude	60	49.466	17.153	2.214
Peace Awareness	60	165.55	22.051	2.846

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t-test	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	32.184	118	0.055

(* Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation

The Independent Sample t-test comparing between yoga attitude and peace awareness of secondary level students yielded t-value of 37.184. It is more than table value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance at 118 df. So, hypothesis-1 is accepted. The two-tailed significance value was 0.055, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between yoga attitude and peace awareness of secondary level students is accepted. Even though the mean scores for peace awareness of students (165.55) is slightly above than yoga attitude of students (49.466), the statistical test indicates that this difference is likely due to chance or sampling error rather than a real difference in the population.

H₀ 2 (i): There are no significant difference between male and female students of yoga attitude.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Male	30	56.5	20.754	3.789
Female	30	42.433	8.097	1.478

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t-test	Df	(Sig. 2-tailed)
	3.458	58	0.001

(* Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation

The Independent Sample t-test comparing the yoga attitude between male and female students yielded t-value of 3.458. It is more than table value (2.00) at 0.05 level of significance at 58 df. So, hypothesis-2 (i) is rejected. The two-tailed significance value was 0.001, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between yoga attitude and peace awareness of secondary level students is rejected. Even though the mean scores for male students of yoga attitude (56.5) is slightly above than female students (42.433), the statistical test indicates that this difference is likely due to chance or sampling error rather than a real difference in the population.

H₀2 (ii): There are no significant difference between male and female students of peace awareness.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Male	30	164.333	20.930	3.821
Female	30	166.766	23.413	4.274

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t-test	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	0.424	58	0.672

(* Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation

The Independent Sample t-test comparing the peace awareness between male and female students yielded t-value of 0.424. It is less than table value (2.00) at 0.05 level of significance at 58 df. So, hypothesis-2 (ii) is accepted. The two-tailed significance value was 0.672, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between male and female students of peace awareness of secondary level students is accepted. Even though the mean scores for female students of peace awareness (166.766) is slightly above than male students (164.333), the statistical test indicates that this difference is likely due to chance or sampling error rather than a real difference in the population.

H₀ 3 (i): There are no significant difference between science and commerce students of yoga attitude.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Science	30	47.1	8.301	1.515
Commerce	30	51.833	22.762	4.155

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t-test	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	1.070	58	0.289

(* Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation

The Independent Sample t-test comparing the yoga attitude between science and commerce students yielded t-value of 1.070. It is less than table value (2.00) at 0.05 level of significance at 58 df. So, hypothesis-3 (i) is accepted. The two-tailed significance value was 0.289, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between science and commerce students of yoga attitude is accepted. Even though the mean scores for commerce students of yoga attitude (51.833) is slightly above than science students (47.1), the statistical test indicates that this difference is likely due to chance or sampling error rather than a real difference in the population.

H₀3 (ii): There are no significant difference between science and commerce students of peace awareness.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Science	30	172.166	19.111	3.489
Commerce	30	158.933	23.097	4.217

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t-test	Df	P-value
	2.417	58	0.018

(* Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation

The Independent Sample t-test comparing the peace awareness between science and commerce students yielded t-value of 2.417. It is more than table value (2.00) at 0.05 level of significance at 58 df.

So, hypothesis-3 (ii) is rejected. The two-tailed significance value was 0.018, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between science and commerce students of peace awareness is rejected. Even though the mean scores for science students of peace awareness (172.166) is slightly above than commerce students (158.933), the statistical test indicates that this difference is likely due to chance or sampling error rather than a real difference in the population.

The Major Findings

1. The mean scores for peace awareness of students showed a significantly higher mean than yoga attitude of students. On the basis of data analyses, peace awareness of students is comparatively better than yoga attitude of students.
2. Male students of yoga attitude showed a significantly higher mean score than female students. On the basis of data analyses, male students of yoga attitude are comparatively better than female students.
3. Female students of peace awareness showed a significantly higher mean score than male students. On the basis of data analyses, female students of peace awareness are comparatively better than male students.
4. Commerce students of yoga attitude showed a significantly higher mean than science students. On the basis of data analyses, commerce students of yoga attitude are comparatively better than science students.
5. Science students of peace awareness showed a significantly higher mean than commerce students. On the basis of data analyses, science students of peace awareness are comparatively better than commerce students.

Conclusion

If education is the only defence against human disaster than peace education is the soul of education that creates the protective covering for human survival on the earth. So, the whole study laid its focus on yoga attitude and peace awareness of secondary level students. Researcher got a result after competition his research work that the students have positive yoga attitude as well as they have positive peace awareness. Here, researcher also found that there lays a moderate positive correlation between yoga attitude and peace awareness of students. Hence, researcher can say that if the family, school authority or government take some active initiatives to promote any one that will influence another to grow up.

Thus, it can simply say that peace and yoga have been the most desired necessities of human life since time immemorial. Human is even more united today in their quest for peace, harmony and better quality of life. A strong need is being felt by educationists and philosophers to accept yoga attitude in human for bringing long-lasting peace.

Educational Implication

- The present study helps to understand students' yoga attitude at Agra district of UP.
- The present study helps to understand students' peace awareness to Agra district of UP.
- The present study helps to understand the interrelationship between students' yoga attitude and students' peace awareness at Agra district of UP.
- The present study may help to educational policy making.

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